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RETRACTED: An acetylcholinesterase-independent mechanism for neurobehavioral impairments after chronic low level exposure to dichlorvos in rats

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Reason: The authors self-plagiarized part of a paper that had already appeared in *Toxicology*, entitled “Role of muscarinic signal transduction and CREB phosphorylation in dichlorvos-induced memory deficits in rats: An acetylcholine independent mechanism”, *Toxicology*, 256 (2009) 175–182, [10.1016/j.tox.2008.11.017](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tox.2008.11.017). One of the conditions of submission of a paper for publication is that authors declare explicitly that their work is original and has not appeared in a publication elsewhere. Re-use of any data should be appropriately cited. As such this article represents a severe abuse of the scientific publishing system. The scientific community takes a very strong view on this matter and we apologize to readers of the journal that this was not detected during the submission process.

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